

I. Foundational Premises

Premise 1:

Paul said, "For I am convinced that neither death nor life, neither angels nor demons, neither the present nor the future, nor any powers, neither height nor depth, nor anything else in all creation, will be able to separate us from the love of God that is in Christ Jesus our Lord."

Premise 2:

The important thing here is to distinguish between love as an emotion and love as a relationship. When someone loves A, it is love as an emotion. When A and B love each other, it is love as a relationship. In the former, the relationship is secondary, and in the latter, the relationship is essential. Christianity does not say that God is satisfied with the former because the former is satisfied since God already loves all humans absolutely. However, the love that Christianity is concerned with is the latter, that is, love as a relationship. A relationship, by definition, requires at least two entities. The moment you completely remove one party, you have destroyed the fundamental prerequisite for the existence of the relationship. Relationships are inherently relational. A unilateral relationship cannot remain unilateral like a coin. Even memories or feelings about past relationships are not relationships themselves; they are psychological artifacts. In the Christian definition, hell is a relational concept, not a place, and the absence of God is hell. However, the reason God is absent is not that God does not go there, but because the people in hell reject God.

This means that rejecting God is rejecting a relationship with God and rejecting God's love. If we deny these, we must argue that hell is not a place where God does not exist, and that rejecting God does not mean rejecting God's love, which goes against the core Christian creed. The important point here is that God is not omnipotent in relationships but is greatly affected by the state of humans. Therefore, to argue that God is not affected by the loss of relationships due to temporary annihilation because He transcends time and space, we must argue that God is not affected by the state of humans.

Otherwise, if He were affected by the state of humans, He would also be affected by the state of temporary annihilation. Then, God should not be affected by the relationship with humans who actively reject God in hell. Another important point is that God is affected by the "human condition." One could argue that God is beyond time and space and therefore cannot be affected by the temporary disappearance of humans. However, by that logic, God should not be affected by the temporary defection or betrayal of humans. Jesus clearly said that He is very happy when the lost sheep returns to Him. The crucial argument here cannot be

made unless: 1. God is not affected by the human condition, or 2. Temporary conditions do not matter to God. But if the latter is true, then God is hardly affected by a child being hurt or in pain, because the child's pain is often temporary. If we claim that God transcends time and space and is not bound by human relationalism, what does that mean? So, 1. Is it possible to have a relationalism that is not bound by human relationalism without committing logical errors? 2. If God's relationalism transcends human relationalism, then how on earth do humans relate to God? If you claim that human relationalism does not work with God, let us assume that we introduce the concept of a relationship that transcends time and space. However, humans are bound by time and space, and love as a relationship cannot be one-sided.

Moreover, God is affected by the state of humans bound by time and space, as argued earlier. Therefore, if humans disappear even temporarily, their relationship with God should actually be affected. This is because love as a relationship cannot be one-sided, and God is also affected by the state of humans. If a love relationship that is not affected by the state of humans is formed between humans and God, what kind of relationship is it? If a "relationship" can be maintained despite the temporary disappearance of humans due to the love of God that transcends time and space, then you are the one who must provide the basis for it. I hope you will prove it. If not, I too can justify numerous dogmatisms based on mystery.

II. Argument Points

Point 3:

If it is argued that God can love in a way that contradicts the basic concept of love because He transcends time and space, then it is a logical contradiction. This is because the definition of love is a relationship, and a relationship requires the existence of the persons forming the relationship. Therefore, even the love between the lover (God) and the loved one ultimately requires the existence of the loved one. Thus, love that does not require the existence of the loved one is a logical contradiction. However, if it is argued that such love is possible because God transcends time and space, then it must be argued that God can create a square with five angles because He transcends time and space.

Point 4:

Christian annihilationists claim that the souls of humans disappear, even temporarily.

Point 5:

If humans disappear completely, even temporarily, then the love between God and man can no longer continue, according to the second definition.

Point 6:

If point 5 is true, then Premise 1 is wrong, because the love between man and God cannot be destroyed by external factors.

Point 7:

If the annihilationist claim is true, then either the love between God and man can be destroyed by external factors, or Premise 2 is wrong.

Point 8:

If you claim that divine and human love can operate in different ways, then you are claiming a square with five sides. This is because the definition of love fundamentally presupposes a relationship, and a relationship necessarily requires the existence of two people in some way. If you reject that, then dry water should also be possible. What do you think?

Point 9:

It can be argued that the temporary extinction of the soul is not external. If so, then the union of man and God is not eternal from any perspective.

Point 10:

Just because God transcends time and space does not mean that He transcends time and space in His relationship with man. If so, why did Jesus grieve when Lazarus died? The problem with God's transcendence of time and space is that just because God transcends time and space, it does not mean that man transcends time and space. Important point: The covenant between the Jews and God is a kind of relationship. However, the continuity of the relationship depended on the Jews. However, God transcended time and space. However, in the covenant with the Jews, the relationship between God and the Jews depended on the state of the Jews, which was limited in time and space. This is because the relationship is fundamentally reciprocal.

When A and B are in a relationship with each other, if A breaks the relationship with B, A and B can no longer be in a relationship. Therefore, the important thing is that the only thing that changes in the relationship between God and man is the state of man, so God's transcendence of time and space in the relationship between man and God cannot solve this problem. This is because the state of man does not transcend time and space. It is not enough for God to keep the covenant. The state of man is important. Because the covenant is a relationship. The only

thing I emphasize here is that the Bible testifies that in the relationship between man and God, God is always fixed and unchanging, but man continues to change with the flow of time, and this continuously changes the relationship between God and man. So God transcends time and space, but in the relationship between God and man, the state of man, bound by time and space, continues or abolishes the relationship. Therefore, the temporary disappearance of man also affects the state of man, and thus the relationship between God and man. Here, I always emphasize that even if God transcends time and space, the relationship between humans and God is affected by the state of humans bound to time and space, and so the love relationship between humans and God is also affected by the change in the state of humans. If you insist otherwise, isn't God affected by the state of humans in the relationship with humans who actively reject him?

If not, then the relationship would be a really strange relationship. Temporary but complete disappearance is not the same as sleep. Because sleep does not require the disappearance of existence. Sleep is simply a state in which consciousness becomes less active potentially and we do not remember what we were doing when we were sleeping. However, complete disappearance of consciousness is a problem. I can read a book whether the light is very bright or very dim. However, if there is no light at all, I cannot read a book. Whether the activity index of consciousness is very high or low, we can maintain a relationship. However, if the existence of consciousness completely disappears, it is impossible to maintain a relationship. If one denies everything and claims that the relationship between God and man remains unchanged even though man is temporarily but completely annihilated, then one must also claim that the relationship between man and God remains unchanged even though man actively rejects God.

This is because for the former to be true, the relationship between God and man must not be affected by the state of man. And if it is true, then the former claim does not hold. If you insist on applying the purely human concept of relationship to God, then the relationship that humans can have is ultimately a personal relationship. Therefore, God approaches humans with the concept of relationship in order to have a relationship with them.

Otherwise, you must completely reject the Christian doctrine that humans and God have a personal relationship. If the relationship between humans and God is a personal relationship, then this relationship is bound by the concept of relationship that I have mentioned. The really important point: I'm talking about purely personal relationships. And in Christianity, the relationship between God and man is a personal relationship. And a personal relationship is the relationship of premise 1. If not, then we have to reject the notion that the relationship between

man and God is a personal relationship.

III. Objections and Counter-Arguments

Objection:

The relationship with God can be severed owing to human error or rejection. Since the wages of sin is death, temporary extinction after death is inevitable.

Counter-argument:

While it is true that the relationship with God can be temporarily severed due to human error or rejection, it must involve an active rejection by humans. Therefore, the wages of sin is not only death but also hell; that is, hell is a state in which humans actively reject their relationship with God.

Let us assume that Paul died and temporarily experienced what might be termed eternal extinction, thereby temporarily deviating from his relationship with God. In this scenario, Paul fell into hell. However, if Paul fell into hell despite possessing true faith, who should be held responsible for this state? Humans are not accountable for lacking their own immortal souls; rather, God should be held responsible. Consequently, God sends innocent people to hell.

Moreover, if it is argued that humans must inevitably experience temporary extinction as a result of sin, then Christians are effectively asserting that they harbour some form of sin despite Christ's sacrifice—since the wages of sin is death. If this were the case, then Christ's atonement did not fully atone for all sins. Were it perfect, no sin could ever bind us. Therefore, unless one contends that Christ's sacrifice was imperfect, the claim that a true believer experiences temporary extinction is absurd.

Counterargument:

This claim does not refute the theory of soul sleep, which posits a sleep-like state rather than one of temporary, perfect extinction.

Counterargument:

The Jews did not believe in any form of conscious activity after death, denying the immortality of the soul and asserting that humans do not exist in an active state of consciousness until the resurrection. Therefore, if we claim that some form of self, or soul, persists after death, does this not amount to a kind of immortality of the soul? Consequently, my claim is that Christianity must presuppose some form of the survival of consciousness after death, and since soul sleep does not assume the extinction of the soul, it is not the central target of this criticism.